

1 **Sorption of ionic liquids in soil enriched with polystyrene microplastic reveals independent**
2 **behavior of cations and anions**

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25 of the manuscript

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29 **Keywords:** sorption isotherms; cationic surfactants; soil environment; herbicidal ionic liquids; choline.

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38 **ABSTRACT**

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Recently, much attention has been focused on the application of the Ionic Liquids (ILs) with herbicidal activity in agriculture. It has been suggested that through the appropriate selection of cations and anions, one can adjust the properties of ILs, particularly the hydrophobicity, solubility, bioavailability, toxicity. In practical agricultural conditions, it will be beneficial to reduce the mobility of herbicidal anions, such as the commonly applied 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid [2,4-D] in the soil. Furthermore, microplastics are becoming increasingly prevalent in the soil, potentially stimulating herbicidal sorption. Therefore, we investigated whether cations in ILs influence the mobility of anions in OECD soil supplemented with polystyrene microplastic (PS). For this purpose, we used the 2,4-D based ILs consisting of: a hydrophilic choline cation [Chol][2,4-D] and a hydrophobic choline cation with a C₁₂-chain [C₁₂Chol][2,4-D]. Characterization of selected micropolystyrene was carried out using the BET sorption-desorption isotherm, particle size distribution and changes in soil sorption parameters such as soil sorption capacity and cation exchange capacity. Based on the batch sorption experiment, the effect of microplastic on the sorption of individual cations and anions in soil contaminated with micropolystyrene was evaluated. The results obtained indicate that the introduction of a 1-10 % (w/w) PS resulted in an 18-23 % increase of the soil sorption capacity. However, the sorption of both ILs' cations increased only by 3-5 %. No sorption of the [2,4-D] anion was noted. This suggests that cations and anions forming ILs, behave independently of each other in the environment. The results indicate the fact that ILs upon introduction into the environment are not a new type of emerging contaminant, but rather a typical mixture of ions. It is worth noting that when analyzing the behavior of ILs in the environment, it is necessary to follow the fate of both cations and anions.

66 1. INTRODUCTION

67

68 The agricultural sector would not survive as an efficient and feasible entity without the invention of
69 plant protection products such as herbicides. Till this day, their worldwide use has raised many
70 discussions related to their negative impact on the environment and human health (Bernardes et al.,
71 2015; Nicolopoulou-Stamati et al., 2016). Therefore, an intense search is currently being conducted to
72 find alternative solutions that are less destructive and more environmentally friendly. Notably, the main
73 adverse effects of herbicides involve their volatility, their high mobility in the soil, the need for
74 additional adjuvants and the unintended acquisition of herbicidal resistance by plants (Arias-Estévez et
75 al., 2008; Curran, 2016). Unfortunately, the improvement of herbicides has slowed down since no new
76 groups of chemicals have been discovered to possess novel mechanisms of interacting with plants
77 (Duke, 2012).

78 Thus, scientists are investigating how to improve the performance of current herbicides through
79 modifying their chemical compositions. Over the past 15 years, much attention has been focused on a
80 group of compounds called ionic liquids (ILs) (Randviir et al., 2014; Talapin and Shevchenko, 2016).
81 Among severally proposed ideas, the concept of converting herbicides into ILs has emerged, thus
82 creating the novel category of herbicidal ionic liquids (HILs) (Wilms et al., 2020). The majority of HILs
83 are based on an herbicidal anion and a suitable organic cation which, through its characteristics, dictates
84 the properties of the entire ionic pair (Choudhary et al., 2017). The most impactful advantage is the
85 heightened herbicidal activity of HILs compared to the standard commercial formulations of herbicides
86 (Niu et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2015) their lower-volatility, higher stability and reduced toxicity (Pernak et
87 al., 2020; Piotrowska et al., 2018, 2017), what makes it possible to use lower doses during spraying
88 procedures which supports the framework of green chemistry (Earle and Seddon, 2000; Welton, 2011).
89 Moreover, numerous authors claim that the introduction of a hydrophobic cation translates directly into
90 an increase in the hydrophobicity of the entire IL. This facilitates the possibility to, for example, increase
91 the soil sorption of easily leachable herbicidal anions, such as 2-methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid
92 (MCPA) or 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D). Thus, for this to occur, it is common practice to

93 pair herbicidal anions with the appropriately suited hydrophobic cations (Kowalska et al., 2021;
94 Stepnowski et al., 2007).

95 However, the true behaviour of ILs in the environment remains a large unknown as no one has fully
96 explored their fate in this respect. Therefore, a key issue to investigate is whether the ILs' integral
97 cationic-anionic pair still exists as a whole entity in the environment.

98 This knowledge is essential to predict how herbicidal ILs will undergo various processes such as
99 sorption and biodegradation. To date, the available publications predominantly focus on studies
100 conducted in aqueous and soil environments for the simplest ILs, consisting of an organic cation and an
101 inorganic anion (Maculewicz et al., 2022; Mrozik et al., 2013, 2012, 2009).

102 Yet, it should certainly be emphasised that IL interactions in the soil environment are more complex in
103 comparison to those occurring in the aquatic environment. This is attributed to many diverse and
104 intricate factors that can affect the biodegradation rate or sorption effectiveness of various xenobiotics
105 (Fantke, et al., 2017). Moreover, it should be noted that the efficacy of sorption of a particular herbicide
106 in the soil may be dependent, in amongst others features, on the content of organic matter (e.g. humic
107 acids) as well as mineral matter (e.g. iron, aluminium oxides etc.) (Werner et al., 2013).

108 Furthermore, as of recent, a significant attentiveness has appeared to be directed towards the commonly
109 occurring micro/nanoplastics (MNPs) found in agricultural soil (micro size: 5 mm-100 nm and nano
110 size <100 nm). Such MNPs can distinctly alter the properties and functioning of the soil environment
111 (Galloway et al., 2017; Gangadoo et al., 2020). The creation of such pollutants is manifold and occurs
112 during processes such as abrasion, mulching, the agricultural use of compost and sewage sludge (Yu
113 and Flury, 2021). There are many indicators that suggest that as the variety and mass-scale production
114 of polymers increases, their presence in the natural environment will also rise. From a statistical point
115 of view, approximately 63,000-430,000 t of MNPs enter EU agricultural land from sewage sludge per
116 year (Nizzetto et al., 2016). Additionally, per annum, there has been on average 6 kg/ha of MNPs
117 originating from compost and it has been noted that approx. 72-260 kg/ha of MNPs have risen from
118 various agricultural foils (Bläsing and Amelung, 2018; Nizzetto et al., 2016).

119 Besides the aforementioned data, it has already been proven that MNPs indeed change the sorption
120 processes of xenobiotics in the soil environment (Fang et al., 2019; Šunta et al., 2020). The evidence of

121 the ability of plastic sorbing herbicides has appeared in scientific research as early as the 1980s. An
122 exemplary case of such studies involved the ability of the herbicide hexazinone to adsorb on polystyrene
123 (Bouchard and Lavy, 1985).

124 From a scientific standpoint, it will be intriguing to assess how the presence of MNPs influences the
125 sorption process of IL cations and anions, whether the cation and anion, which form an IL, will remain
126 as an integral pair in the soil environment; or whether the cationic-anionic forces of attraction will be
127 overcome, breaking the ionic pair into two separate, mobile entities in the soil.

128 In our previous studies, we observed that in simple soil systems, the hydrophobic cations become
129 strongly sorbed while the anions retain their mobility (Parus et al., 2023; Woźniak-Karczewska et al.,
130 2022). Yet, could the presence of varying concentrations of MNPs alter the above-noted trends?

131 Therefore, the purpose of our study was to investigate the effect of polystyrene microplastic on the
132 sorption processes of ILs exhibiting herbicidal activity in an OECD model soil.

133 A common herbicide known as 2,4-D was used for the study. This anion was individually combined
134 with two cations of different hydrophobicity, namely choline hydrophilic [Chol] and a hydrophobic
135 choline derivative, which was modified by introducing a C₁₂ chain [C₁₂Chol].

136 The analysis of the behavior of the cations and anions, which constitute the IL, in a soil environment
137 that is contaminated with MNP is truly crucial. Such studies will help to understand further whether ILs
138 are a potentially new emerging contaminant.

139

140 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

141 *2.1. Synthesis of ionic liquids displaying herbicidal activity*

142

143 The synthesis and characteristics of [Chol][2,4-D] and [C₁₂Chol][2,4-D] were previously described by
144 (Praczyk et al., 2012) and (Marcinkowska et al., 2017). Firstly, [2,4-D] was neutralized with
145 appropriately measured stoichiometric amounts of potassium hydroxide in methanol solvent. Secondly,
146 the solvent was evaporated using a rotary vacuum evaporator in order to obtain potassium salts of [2,4-
147 D]. Subsequently, the salts were dried in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 48 hours.

148 Next, choline chloride [Chol][Cl] or *N*-dodecylcholine chloride [C₁₂Chol][Cl] (0.01 mol) was dissolved
 149 in 10 mL of methanol in a reaction vessel equipped with a mechanical stirrer. Then, a 2% molar excess
 150 (10.2 mmol) of potassium salt [2,4-D] was added (previously dissolved in 10 mL of methanol) to initiate
 151 ion exchange. After 60 minutes, the mixture was cooled to 0 °C. The precipitated potassium chloride
 152 was filtered off and the solvent was evaporated from the filtrate. The obtained products were further
 153 purified through the addition of a small portion (10-15 mL) of acetone and subsequently, the undissolved
 154 impurities were removed. Then, the solvent was evaporated from filtrates. Finally, the obtained products,
 155 namely [Chol][2,4-D] and [C₁₂Chol][2,4-D], were dried at 50 °C for 24 h under reduced pressure. The
 156 yields of the reactions were sufficiently large and exceeded > 95 % for both ILs.

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158 2.2. Soil characteristics

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160 The OECD soil (soil prepared in accordance with the guidelines Organization for Economic Co-
 161 operation and Development) was purchased from Tigret Ltd. (Warsaw, Poland). The composition and
 162 characteristics of the OECD soil have been provided in Table 1.

163

164 **Table 1.** Composition and characteristics of the OECD soil.

Soil composition	Total carbon	pH	Water holding capacity	Cation exchange capacity
70 % air-dried quartz sand, 20 % kaolin clay, 10 % peat.	5 %	6.5 (in H ₂ O)	40 %	8.76 cmol/kg

165 Data representing the average of a triplicate soil analysis (standard mean error: ± 5 %, n=3)

166

167 2.3. Microplastic preparation

168

169 The polystyrene (PS) with the trade name Empera 124L (Brenntag Polska Ltd., Poland) was the utilized
 170 microplastic throughout the undertaken research. The PS density (sourced from ISO 1183) was 1.04
 171 g/mL, the tensile stress at yield (according to ISO 527-1.2) was denoted as 50 MPa and the vicat
 172 softening temperature (in agreement with ISO 306) was approx. 87 °C (B50). This particular PS in its
 173 commercial form constitutes of cylindrical granules with dimensions ranging from 2 to 3 mm. In order

174 to obtain the desired microplastic, PS was ground in dry ice to prevent the plasticization of the polymer
175 as well as to increase the grinding efficiency. The grinding was carried out through the use of an ultra-
176 centrifugal mill (ZM 200, Retsch, Germany) with a vibrating feeder (DR 100, Retsch, Germany). The
177 subsequent rotor speed was set to 10000 rpm and a ring sieve of a mesh size of 0.5 mm was used to
178 enhance the grinding efficiency.

179 The particle size distribution of microplastics was then measured using a Mastersizer 3000 analyzer
180 (Malvern Instruments Ltd., UK).

181

182 *2.4. Textural characterization of the PS microplastic*

183 In this section, the surface area (A_{BET}), average pore diameter (S_p) and total pore volume (V_p) of the PS
184 microplastic were determined based on a low-temperature sorption of N_2 at -196 °C. This was achieved
185 through using an ASAP 2020 physisorption analyzer (Micromeritics Instrument Co., Norcross, CA,
186 USA). The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) model was utilised to calculate the surface area based on
187 adsorptive data for relative pressure (p/p_0) in the range 0.05-0.30. The pore size distribution and the total
188 volume of the pores were estimated from the desorption isotherm based on the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda
189 (BJH) method. This was solved through the use of the Halsey equation. Moreover, prior to measurement,
190 the analyzed sample was degassed under a vacuum at 80 °C for 10 h.

191

192 *2.5. Determination of the sorption capacity of PS, OECD soil and OECD + PS*

193

194 The Kappen's method (Jaremko and Kalembasa, 2014; Kappen, 1929) was applied to investigate the
195 potential interaction of the chosen microplastic with the soil matrix. This was employed in order to
196 investigate if there would be an increase in the sorption capacity of OECD soil in the presence of
197 microplastics. Firstly, the sorption capacity of PS at 1, 2, 5 and 10 wt. % (weight percent) was
198 determined. Secondly, the sorption capacity of the pure OECD soil was analysed. Lastly, the final
199 sorption assessment involved the combination of OECD soil with 1, 2, 5 and 10 wt. % PS, respectively.
200 The concentration range that was chosen was based on prior publications, which claimed that the
201 presence of microplastics in agricultural fields can reach values of up to a maximum of 10 %

202 concentration (de Souza Machado et al., 2019; Fuller and Gautam, 2016; Hüffer et al., 2019).
203 A microplastic with a particle size similar to our PS microplastic was used by Chen et al. (Chen et al.,
204 2021). This size was chosen because microplastics <1 mm in size predominate in soils, as previously
205 reported (Lv et al., 2019; Zhang and Liu, 2018). In addition, the sorption capacity, defined as the sum
206 of the hydrolytic acidity value and the sum of exchangeable alkaline cations, was calculated using
207 formula (1) for each sample:

$$209 \qquad \qquad \qquad T = H + S \qquad \qquad \qquad (1)$$

210 where: T – soil sorption capacity [cmol_{c+}/kg], H – sum of the hydrolytic acidity [cmol_{H+}/kg], S - sum of
211 exchangeable base cations [cmol/kg].

212
213 *2.5.1. Hydrolytic acidity*

214
215 Hydrolytic acidity is defined as the soil acidity that is formulated through the presence of an acidic
216 hydroxyl or carboxyl group (Chestworth, 2008).

217 The air-dried soil was sieved through a 1 mm mesh sieve. Then 150 mL of 1 mol/L sodium acetate
218 solution was added to 60 g of sieved soil. The suspension was shaken for 1h in a conical flask of about
219 250 mL on a rotary shaker operating at 230 rpm. The contents were then filtered (0.22 μm PTFE syringe
220 filter). The resulting filtrate was titrated with a 0.1 mol/L sodium hydroxide solution in the presence of
221 phenolphthalein indicator. The hydrolytic acidity values were then calculated from the amount of
222 sodium hydroxide solution consumed using the following formula (2):

$$224 \qquad \qquad \qquad H = V \cdot c_M \cdot 5 \cdot 1.5 \qquad \qquad \qquad (2)$$

225 where: H - hydrolytic acidity [cmol_{H+}/kg], V - the volume of NaOH used to neutralize the resulting acid,
226 c_M - NaOH molar concentration [mol/L], 5 - conversion factor for 100 g of soil (since 50 mL of filtrate
227 corresponds to a weight of 20 g of soil), 1.5 - Kappen's coefficient, correction for incomplete
228 displacement of hydrogen and aluminum ions during a single treatment of soil with an ammonium
229 acetate solution.

230 2.5.2. *Exchangeable alkaline cations*

231

232 Exchangeable alkaline cations are defined by the amount of acidity contributed by free hydrogen ions
233 and acidic cations (e.g. Al³⁺) that are thus neutralized by a NaOH base (Chestworth, 2008). To 20 g of
234 air-dry soil, 200 mL of 0.1 mol/L hydrochloric acid solution were added. Next, the collected suspension
235 was shaken in a conical flask of approx. 250 mL capacity on a rotary shaker (at 230 rpm) at room
236 temperature for 1 hour and then filtered through a 0.22 µm PTFE syringe filter. The filtrate was titrated
237 with 0.1 mol/L sodium hydroxide solution in the presence of phenolphthalein indicator. Subsequently,
238 the sum of exchangeable alkali cations was calculated from the amount of sodium hydroxide solution
239 used, with the following formula:

240

241
$$S = (b - a) \cdot c_M \cdot \frac{200}{40 \cdot \frac{V}{V_c}} \quad (3)$$

242 where: S - sum of alkaline cations, [cmol_{c+}/kg], a - volume [mL] of 0.1 M NaOH consumed in the
243 titration of the analysed sample, b - volume [mL] of 0.1 M NaOH expended during the titration with 0.1
244 M HCl (the derived average of repetitions), V - volume of extract used for titration, V_c - volume of 0.1
245 M HCl solution used for the soil extraction, c_M - molar concentration of NaOH solution, $200/(40 \cdot V/V_c)$ -
246 conversion coefficient per 100 g of soil (where the soil to solution ratio is 1:5).

247
$$\frac{200}{40 \cdot \frac{V}{V_c}}$$

248 this fragment should not be in italics. I am attaching the correctly formatted $200/(40 \cdot V/V_c)$

249 2.6. *Sorption of ionic liquids on PS, OECD soil and PS + OECD*

250

251 The experiments were carried out according to the stipulated OECD (2000) guidelines (“OECD/OCDE
252 106. Adsorption - Desorption Using a Batch Equilibrium Method.,” 2000) for the 2,4-D sodium salt and
253 [Chol][2,4-D] or [C₁₂Chol][2,4-D] combination. Thus, the standard concentration of active substance
254 [2,4-D] for each treatment was equal to 10 mg/L. Firstly, the OECD soil was sterilized using an
255 autoclave for 20 minutes at 121 °C. This procedure was repetitively carried out for three consecutive

256 days. Between sterilizations, the soil was dried at 60 °C in agreement with the procedure described by
257 Shen et al. (Shen et al., 2018).

258 Therefore, in centrifuge tubes, 5 mL of the corresponding HIL and 1 g of dried sterile OECD soil were
259 mixed with 1, 2, 5 and 10% wt. % PS, respectively. The polypropylene tubes were then shaken on an
260 orbital shaker at 240 rpm at 20 ± 1 °C in the dark (to avoid photodegradation). Samples were collected
261 after 24 hours and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The resulting supernatant was then filtered
262 through a 0.22 µm PTFE syringe filter (Whatman® Puradisc, Sigma Aldrich, UK). In a similar manner,
263 this procedure was also carried out for the OECD soil system, in which 1 g of OECD soil was mixed
264 with 5 mL of the corresponding HIL (without the addition of PS). In addition, treatments in which PS
265 was the only substance were also examined. For such an analysis, each PS sample was supplemented
266 with 5 mL of HIL at a mass of 0.01, 0.02, 0.05 and 0.1 g of PS (these values correspond to chosen
267 concentration range of 1, 2, 5 and 10 wt. % of PS, respectively).

268 The concentration of cations and anions was determined using the LC-MS/MS equipment. Possible
269 sorption of HILs on the surface of PP centrifuge tubes was also examined. In order to do so, blanks were
270 prepared by shaking a 5 mL solution of the HIL without any soil and microplastic present. Additionally,
271 1 g of soil with 5 mL of water was also tested, notably, without the analyzed HILs present. All
272 experiments were performed in triplicate. The efficiency of the adsorption process of herbicide cations
273 and anions of ionic liquids in the soil was calculated through the following formula (4):

274

$$275 \quad \text{removal \%} = \frac{c_0 - c_e}{c_0} \cdot 100 \% \quad (4)$$

276 where: c_0 and c_e are the initial and equilibrium concentrations of the herbicide present in solution (mg/L).

277 Adsorption isotherms were also determined in this experiment. The exact procedure for determination
278 has been described by (Woźniak-Karczewska et al., 2022).

279

280 *2.7. LC-MS/MS analysis*

281

282 The LC-MS/MS analysis consisted of the use of UltiMate 3000 RSLC from Dionex (Sunnyvale, CA,
 283 USA) alongside the API 4000 QTRAP triple quadrupole mass spectrometer from AB Sciex (Foster City,
 284 CA, USA). The samples (with a volume of 5 μ L) were injected into a Gemini-NX C18 column (100 mm
 285 \times 2.0 mm I.D.; 3 μ m) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA) thermostated at 35 $^{\circ}$ C. A two-phase
 286 gradient elution composed of a 5 mM aqueous solution of ammonium acetate (A) and methanol (B) was
 287 used with a flow-rate set to 0.3 mL/min. The mobile phase gradient employed for the determination of
 288 the [2,4-D] anion and the [Chol] cation was as follows: 0 min – 50 % B; 1 min – 50 % B; 2 min – 100
 289 % B; 3 min – 100 % B. Likewise, [C₁₂Chol] was determined in a gradient of 0 min – 80 % B; 2 min –
 290 100 % B; 4 min – 100 % B. The effluent from the column was directed to the electrospray ionization
 291 source (the Turbo Ion Spray) which has been operated in a negative ion mode for anions and in a positive
 292 ion mode for cations. The following settings of the required source parameters were applied: curtain gas
 293 10 psi, nebulizer gas 40 psi, auxiliary gas 45 psi, temperature 450 $^{\circ}$ C, ion spray voltage +/- 4500 V.
 294 Notably, the mass spectrometer working conditions and characteristics of particular ions are listed in
 295 Table 2 below.

296

297 **Table 2.** Parameters of the MS detection.

Analyte	DP (V)	Precursor ion [m/z]	Product ion [m/z]	EP (V)	CE (eV)	CXP (V)
[2,4-D]	-45	219.9	161.9	-10	-23	-8
[Chol]	115	104.0	60.0	3	25	10
[C ₁₂ Chol]	160	257.7	214.1	8	33	13

298 DP – declustering potential, EP – entrance potential, CE – collision energy, CXP – collision cell exit potential

299

300 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

301

302 3.1. Determination of the sorption capacity of PS, OECD soil and PS + OECD

303

304 Prior to the study, we fully characterised the PS in terms of its particle size, adsorption/desorption
 305 isotherms, surface area and pore volume etc. Hence, we will refer to these parameters in the
 306 Supplementary Information provided, namely: Figures S1 and S2, Tables S1 and S2.

307 Assessment of soil sorption capacity and cation exchange capacity (CEC) are among the key parameters
 308 for determining soil properties. The introduction of fertilizers, as well as xenobiotics including
 309 microplastics, can change soil chemistry, and this can alter both parameters. Hence, there is a need for
 310 the analysis of the change in sorption capacity and cation exchange capacity after the introduction of
 311 micropolystyrene into soil.

312 Analysing the sorption capacity of PS, one can see that it increased from 1.35 to 1.78 [cmol/kg] as
 313 amount of microplastic present increased (Table 3). A similar observation was made when microplastics
 314 were added to the OECD soil.

315 The introduction of 2 wt. % of PS to the soil resulted in an 18 % (0.81 [cmol/kg]) increase in the sorption
 316 capacity in comparison to the pure OECD soil. Moreover, a further increase in the PS content, namely
 317 5 or 10 wt. %, amplified the sorption capacity of the soil by 22 % (1.06 [cmol/kg]) and 23 % (1.11
 318 [cmol/kg]), respectively. Thus, the values of the obtained sorption capacity for the OECD soil containing
 319 PS was therefore not equal to the sorption capacities determined for the pure OECD soil sample and the
 320 pure PS sample separately. This should potentially result in higher sorption of the analyzed ILs in the
 321 soil that is enriched with PS.

322

323 **Table 3.** The sorption capacity determined for PS as well as OECD soil (both with and without PS).

System	Sorption capacity [cmol/kg]
1 % PS	1.35 ± 0.06
2 % PS	1.68 ± 0.05
5 % PS	1.69 ± 0.02
10 % PS	1.78 ± 0.27
OECD + 0 % PS*	3.77 ± 0.09
OECD+ 1 % PS*	3.75 ± 0.11
OECD+ 2 % PS*	4.58 ± 0.11
OECD+ 5 % PS*	4.83 ± 0.07
OECD+ 10 % PS*	4.88 ± 0.02

324 ± standard error of the mean of three independent experiments

325 *soil OECD with % PS (w/w) addition

326

327 Notably, the increases in the soil sorption capacity in the soil with PS present should be attributed to the
 328 additional porous structures and reactive surfaces of the microplastic. These elements may influence the
 329 interactions (predominantly the non-specific van-der Waals forces) between PS and the soil. Hence,

330 multiple researchers mainly concentrate on the effects of the presence of MNPs on the soil sorption but
331 they do not focus solely on parameters like cation exchange. Instead, many scientific reports
332 predominantly focus on analysing changes in the structure, bulk density or water capacity of soil thereof
333 (Chen et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2020; J. Li et al., 2021).

334 In our opinion, the studies of the sorption of xenobiotics in soil-microplastic systems are worth to be
335 extended, focusing more on the evaluation of the sorption capacity as well as the cation exchange
336 capacity. The aforementioned two factors both demonstrate certain changes in the potential of the soil
337 sorption complex, i.e. the ability to store ions (mainly cations) through exchange sorption.

338 *3.2. Sorption of herbicidal ionic liquids*

339

340 *3.2.1. Sorption of [Chol] and [C₁₂Chol] cations on PS with its characterisation*

341

342 The PS microplastic used in our analysis has four noteworthy characteristics: average sized (denoted as
343 d_{50}) equal to 276 μm (Figure 1.), low BET surface area
344 ($0.2 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), low total pore volume (0.001 mL/g) and mean pore diameter of 23.1 nm for each PS granule.

345

346

347 **Figure 1.** The particle size distributions (particle volume in %) of polystyrene used in the experiments.

348 The obtained microparticle dimensions ranged from 16.4 to 976 μm

349

350

351 Additionally, the attained N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm for the PS sample is presented in Figure 2
352 below. The interpretation of the aforementioned parameters, i.e. the porous structure of the PS sample,
353 confirm that the hysteresis loops are in agreement with the relative pressure range of $p/p_0=0.48-0.99$.
354 Hence, it is visible that the amount of nitrogen adsorbed slowly increases in the relative pressure range
355 $p/p_0=0-0.82$; above $p/p_0=0.82$ it rapidly increases to reach a maximum value of 0.7 mL/g at $p/p_0=0.99$.

356 Hence the analysed PS material can be classified as type II, which is characterized for non-porous or
357 macroporous materials. This type of isotherm indicates an indefinite multi-layer formation after
358 completion of the monolayer and is found in adsorbents with a wide distribution of pore sizes.

359

360 **Figure 2.** N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms (a) and distribution of pore size (b) of the PS sample.

361

362 Notably, the low value presented by the BET surface area for polystyrene materials was also recognized
363 by Sarkar et al. (Sarkar et al., 2021). Their research demonstrated that polystyrene-based microplastics,
364 such as engineered MPs, raw plastic and semi-environmental plastic, are characterized with a BET
365 surface area of 0.379 m²/g, 0.581 m²/g and 0.618 m²/g, respectively. The PS utilized in our analysis
366 classifies as a typical PS micropolymer.

367 From the obtained data, one can see that the sorption of the [Chol] cation on PS was approx. 3.3 ± 0.4
368 mg/kg, what this corresponds to 16-18 %, as indicated in Table 4. For the hydrophobic [C₁₂Chol] cation,
369 the sorption was in the range of 19-21 %, which is correlated to approx. 4.1 ± 0.5 mg/kg. Compared to
370 available data, similar trends were also observed in the aqueous environment for the commonly used
371 triazole fungicides hexaconazole, myclobutanil, triadimenol, where the increase in adsorption capacity
372 on 1000 mg/L PS was positively related to their hydrophobicity and was 40 µg/g, 20 µg/g, and 10 µg/g,
373 respectively (Fang et al., 2019). An analogous effect was reported for the sorption of sulfamethoxazole,
374 sulfamethazine and cephalosporin C on naturally aged PS microplastics (Guo and Wang, 2019).
375 Evidently, the sorption capacities of herbicidal ILs on polystyrene microplastics obtained within our
376 studies were indeed in an range of results presented for various organic compounds by other scientists
377 (Gong et al., 2019; S. Li et al., 2021).

378 Yet, the minor differences between the sorption of the hydrophilic and hydrophobic cation on PS should
379 still be emphasized.

380 Such a characteristic of PS directly translates into a negligible sorption of the analyzed cations. Notably,
381 18% of the hydrophilic cation was sorbed on a 10 % PS sample, while 23% of the hydrophobic cation
382 was sorbed in an analogous system.

383 Reportedly, the presence of functional groups on the surface of the sorption material also portrays a
384 significant impact during the sorption processes (Gong et al., 2019; Guo and Wang, 2019; Hu et al.,
385 2020; S. Li et al., 2021). In this respect, one can observe that PS is a material poor in functional groups,
386 which means that it is not conducive to the sorption processes. In the assessed PS-xenobiotic system,
387 sorption probably occurs according to the mechanism of π - π , electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions
388 between the analyzed cations and the sorption material, which has also been described by the other
389 authors in their research (Gong et al., 2019; Guo and Wang, 2019; Hu et al., 2020; S. Li et al., 2021).
390 Nevertheless, from our experiments, one can see that the influence of PS is not a determining factor of
391 the cation sorption capacity.

392

393 *3.2.2. Sorption of [Chol] and [C₁₂Chol] cations on the pure OECD soil, without PS*

394

395 Notably, the sorption of the [Chol] cation in the pure OECD soil was approx. 44 %, whereas the sorption
396 of the hydrophobic [C₁₂Chol] cation in the OECD soil was 94.8 %, as displayed in Table 4. Thus, the
397 hydrophobic nature of the [C₁₂Chol] cation results in a greater sorption in the soil in comparison to the
398 hydrophilic [Chol] cation. Such a result was indeed expected due to the various reports supporting such
399 a mechanism (Parus et al., 2023). Moreover, recent studies have indicated that hydrophobic cationic
400 surfactants such as [C₁₂Chol] are strongly sorbed in the soil that consists of mineral and organic
401 components (e.g. humic substances) (Bouras et al., 2010; Gamboa and Olea, 2006; Zhan et al., 2013).
402 As reported by Ishiguro et al. (Ishiguro and Koopal, 2016), the transfer of the surfactant tails of dodecyl-
403 and cetylpyridinium chlorides to the hydrophobic components of humic substances is a common
404 mechanism. A key role in the adsorption of cationic surfactants on negatively charged mineral surfaces
405 is dependent on the positive charges of cations and additionally, hydrophobic interactions created by
406 long alkyl chain presence (Li and Gallus, 2007). Moreover, there are also numerous reports on the
407 sorption of cationic surfactants on silicate clays and metal oxides (Ishiguro and Koopal, 2016; Liu et al.,
408 2021). Based on the adsorption studies of dodecyl trimethylammonium and hexadecyl
409 trimethylammonium onto kaolinite, it was confirmed that the chain length of the surfactant substantially
410 influenced the adsorption efficiency (Li and Gallus, 2007). Therefore, the detected high sorption of the

411 hydrophobic cation compared to the low sorption of hydrophilic cation in the soil is indeed consistent
412 with the results obtained in similar studies, where 2,4-D was bound with betaine [Bet] and [C₁₂Bet]
413 (Woźniak-Karczewska et al., 2022). Likewise, in another study, where herbicidal ILs were used, similar
414 trends were observed. This investigation utilised [Chol][Glyph] and [C₁₂Chol][Glyph], where it was
415 noted that 42 – 45 % of the [Chol] cation was adsorbed for OECD and agricultural soils. On the contrary,
416 the hydrophobic [C₁₂Chol] cation was almost quantitatively adsorbed in both soil types which is certainly
417 a considerable result.

418 Hence, it may be concluded that regardless of whether the analyzed herbicidal IL consists of 2,4-D or
419 glyphosate, the efficiency of the cation sorption primarily depends on the hydrophilic or hydrophobic
420 nature of the cation. Moreover, it is independent of anion type (Parus et al., 2023).

421

422 3.2.3. Sorption of [Chol] and [C₁₂Chol] cations on OECD soil with PS

423

424 The introduction of various amounts of PS (1-10 wt. %) to the OECD soil resulted in the sorption of
425 [Chol] ranging from 44 to 47 % (Table 4). Noticeably, the sorption of the hydrophobic cation [C₁₂Chol]
426 in the pure OECD soil was already high, reaching 94.8 %. Hence, the introduction of PS improved the
427 sorption efficiency by approx. 5 %. Therefore, for both cations, a 3-5 % increase in sorption, in the
428 OECD soil containing PS, was indeed observed. Such an increase in the sorption of the analyzed cations
429 is not a surprising occurrence, since microplastics in the soil act as an additional sorbent (Joo et al.,
430 2021). However, the results indicate that the sorption efficiency is mainly influenced by the soil type.
431 Thus, the addition of a microplastic with a weak porous structure does not result in a statistically large
432 increase in the sorption.

433 Moreover, the slight increase in the sorption in the soil-microplastic system confirms the assumption
434 that the sorption mechanism, based on the interaction of the xenobiotic with functional groups present
435 in the macro- and micropores of the soil, dictates the sorption efficiency.

436 These trends are confirmed by comparative analysis of sorption tests (Table 4) with the results of soil
437 sorption capacity (Table 3). The introduction of micropolystyrene into the soil does not significantly
438 increase the sorption of [Chol] and [C₁₂Chol] cation, because the interaction between micropolystyrene

439 is through $\pi - \pi$ and/or electrostatic interactions, which are much weaker than chemical sorption with
440 soil components.

441 Furthermore, the results obtained by other researchers can also confirm that, for example, the sorption
442 of tetracycline to soil is stronger than that of microplastics. This is attributed to other soil-related
443 interactions such as cation exchange, surface complexation and cation bridging interactions. It was
444 reported that the partition coefficient of tetracycline to soil was 1093 ± 92 L/kg in the concentration
445 range of 0.01-0.1 mg/L (Pan and Chu, 2016). On the contrary, the corresponding coefficient of the
446 selected microplastics (PS, PP and PE) was low, ranging between 160-445 L/kg for higher
447 concentrations (1 mg/L), of course depending on the type of microplastic (Xu et al., 2018).

448 Another exemplary study, conducted by Hu et al. (Hu et al., 2020), investigated the sorption of 17β -
449 estradiol in the soil with a microplastic such as polystyrene. The results of the experiment showed that
450 the adsorption capacity of the microplastic against 17β -estradiol was stronger than that of soil. We
451 believe this is due to the fact that the researchers conducted this particular study in which the soil was
452 mixed with microplastics in a 2:1 ratio. This significantly differs from real systems. Similarly, Chen et
453 al. (Chen et al., 2021) examined the sorption of triclosan on polyethylene as well as the sorption of
454 polystyrene microplastics on soil particles. The results showed that the sorption potential of the soil was
455 notably lower than that of the microplastic, despite the ratio of soil to microplastic being 1:1. Thus, in
456 order to obtain reliable data, it is crucial to conduct research on the actual amounts of microplastics that
457 occur in agricultural fields. In our assumptions, we took into consideration the worst possible outcome
458 in which the soil was enriched by as much as 10% wt. PS. According to many researchers, such an
459 amount is seen as a significantly high level of microplastic contamination (De Souza Machado et al.,
460 2018; Fuller and Gautam, 2016; Hüffer et al., 2019; Rillig, 2018; Yang et al., 2021). However, we
461 believe that realistically, this contamination could be as low as 1% (Corradini et al., 2019; Katsumi et
462 al., 2021; Scheurer and Bigalke, 2018; Vollertsen and Hansen, 2017; Zhang et al., 2018) (Figure 3).
463 Nonetheless, regardless of the plastic concentration, it was the soil type which was the deciding factor
464 in the sorption process.

465

466 **Figure 3.** Ranges of microplastic concentrations in soil analyzed by different authors

467
468
469
470

Table 4. Adsorption of cations [Chol] and [C₁₂Chol] as well as [2,4-D] anion in OECD soil, with PS.

System	Adsorption [%]			
	[Chol]	[2,4-D]	[C ₁₂ Chol]	[2,4-D]
1 % PS	16.8 ± 0.4	0.0 ± 0.0	20.6 ± 0.5**	0.0 ± 0.0
2 % PS	16.1 ± 0.5	0.0 ± 0.0	18.9 ± 0.6**	0.0 ± 0.0
5 % PS	17.5 ± 0.6	0.0 ± 0.0	18.9 ± 0.4**	0.0 ± 0.0
10 % PS	18.1 ± 0.4	0.0 ± 0.0	20.8 ± 0.4**	0.0 ± 0.0
OECD + 0 % PS*	43.8 ± 0.9	0.0 ± 0.0	94.8 ± 1.3**	0.0 ± 0.0
OECD + 1 % PS*	45.7 ± 1.0	0.0 ± 0.0	97.7 ± 1.7**	0.0 ± 0.0
OECD + 2 % PS*	46.7 ± 1.1	0.0 ± 0.0	97.8 ± 1.7**	0.0 ± 0.0
OECD + 5 % PS*	44.7 ± 0.8	0.0 ± 0.0	97.7 ± 1.7**	0.0 ± 0.0
OECD + 10 % PS*	46.9 ± 1.1	0.0 ± 0.0	97.9 ± 1.7**	0.0 ± 0.0
PP falcon	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	1.7 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0

471 *soil OECD with % PS (w/w) addition

472 ** The sorption values were reduced by the sorption on PP falcon, ± standard error of the mean of three independent
473 experiments

474
475

476 3.2.4. Sorption of [2,4-D] anion on PS and OECD soil, (both with and without PS)

477

478 From the data, one can discern that the herbicidal anion was practically not sorbed in the analyzed soil
479 sample (Table 4).

480 Moreover, the heightened mobility of 2,4-D in loam, silt-loam and sandy-loam soil was also discussed
481 previously by other researchers (Brucha et al., 2021; Meftaul et al., 2020; Morillo et al., 2001). In certain
482 studies, the sorption of the [2,4-D] anion at the 10 % level was described for herbicidal ILs with the use
483 of betaine cations in a real agricultural soil (Woźniak-Karczewska et al., 2022). Moreover, in an
484 agricultural soil, 2,4-D is capable of only low sorption due to the presence of specific minerals. In some
485 instances, 2,4-D was even able to sorb, for example, onto quartz (Clausen et al., 2001). Furthermore,

486 due to the presence of COO⁻ groups, the herbicide has been adsorbed onto the positive sites of an α -
 487 Al₂O₃ surface as well as that of calcite (Werner et al., 2013).

488 At present, there are only a few publications that have investigated the sorption of pesticides on
 489 polystyrene microplastics in a soil environment. Predominantly, the effects of microplastics (for
 490 example polyethylene beads, polyvinyl chloride, tire fragments) on 2,4-D, glyphosate and atrazine have
 491 been deeply analyzed in an aqueous environment (Fatema and Farenhorst, 2022). Certain authors have
 492 revealed a weak affinity for microplastics (< 6 %) for herbicides, except for the sorption of glyphosate
 493 on PVC (32-36 %) (Fatema and Farenhorst, 2022). This is not a surprising phenomenon, since
 494 glyphosate is capable of being sorbed between 30-40 % in the soil (Parus et al., 2023). However, it is
 495 worth mentioning that glyphosate is a zwitterion and, through the presence of a positive charge, it will
 496 interact with negative charges of soil constituents (Fliss et al., 2021). In Table 5, more information is
 497 presented on the sorption of the 2,4-D.

498

499 **Table 5.** [2,4-D] herbicide sorption on different types of soils as well as various microplastics.

2,4-D herbicide sorption	Tested system	Reference
No sorption, lack of integrity of the ion pair in the ionic liquid	OECD soil	This study
Constant low 2,4-D soil sorption (approx. 4-5 mg/kg), regardless of the hydrophobicity of the ionic liquid cation	fine-grained sandy loam type OL	Woźniak-Karczewska et al. (Woźniak-Karczewska et al., 2022)
Low 2,4-D sorption (K _D = 0.66 L/kg)	calcareous soil	Ozbay et al. (Ozbay et al., 2018)
Only 0.5 - 3.5 mg/kg 2,4-D sorption	sandy-loam and loamy-clay soils	Spark et al. (Spark K and Swift R, 2002)
q _{max} values for soils with low carbon content in range of 13-35 mg/kg	loam, silt-loam, clay, sandy-loam soils etc.	Meftaul et al. (Meftaul et al., 2020)
Less than 0.15 µg/L 2,4-D sorption	0.1 g of microplastics (i.e. fiber, polyethylene beads, polyvinyl chloride, and tire fragments)	Fatema et al. (Fatema and Farenhorst, 2022)

500

501 The partial sorption of the [Chol] cation and almost quantitative sorption of the [C₁₂Chol] cation did not
 502 substantially contribute to the sorption of the anion [2,4-D]. This is solid evidence that neither
 503 hydrophilic nor hydrophobic herbicidal IL cations have an effect on the sorption of the [2,4-D] anion.
 504 In fact, if the interactions between a cation and an anion in herbicidal ILs were sufficiently strong and

505 formed an ionic pair, a retention effect of the anions should be observed. Similarly, the lack of impact
506 of anions on the total sorption of imidazole-based ILs was examined by Dong et al. (Dong et al., 2018).
507 Moreover, a study conducted by Stepnowski et al (Mrozik et al., 2013, 2012; Stepnowski et al., 2007)
508 reported that cations were strongly sorbed in the soil, while the simple inorganic anions, such as Cl^- or
509 Br^- , were not analyzed and thus considered insignificant due to soil the properties.
510 Hence, the generalization that the sorption of the entire IL is dependent solely on the sorption of the
511 cation can be deemed as inaccurate. The omission of the role of even a simple inorganic anion leaves a
512 large gap in the understanding of the fate of ILs in the environment. This is why our research is so
513 important as it shows that ILs, when introduced into the soil environment, act independently. Thus, our
514 research can counter the present belief that ILs act as new, emerging contaminants as suggested in some
515 reports (Oskarsson and Wright, 2019; Wei et al., 2021).

516

517 *3.3. Sorption isotherms*

518

519 In order to gain a more complete insight into the behavior of ILs, the analysis of cationic and anionic
520 sorption isotherms was undertaken. Based on the OECD recommendations (Kowalska et al., 2021) as
521 well as the published data, leading studies of the sorption of ILs have used the Freundlich isotherm
522 (Krop et al., 2020). This model has been successfully applied in previous studies of the sorption of
523 xenobiotics on microplastics (Elizalde-Velázquez et al., 2020; Hüffer et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020)
524 (Figure S1-S2 and Table S1- S2 in ESI). The position of the isotherms on the graphs representing both
525 cations, namely [Chol] and [C_{12}Chol], allows us to conclude that there is no statistical differences in the
526 sorption of both cations in the analyzed systems (both soil OECD and soil OECD with PS) (Figure 4).

527

528 **Figure 4.** Adsorption isotherms for [Chol] (a) and [C_{12}Chol] (b) cations for the OECD + 2 % PS system.

529

530 The calculated K_f values are commonly used in order to measure the efficiency of the adsorption process
531 (Ozbay et al., 2018). One can see that there is a direct proportionality between the measured quantities,
532 namely: the higher the K_f value, the higher the sorption of the analyzed xenobiotic (Peruchi et al., 2015).

533 The hydrophilic [Chol] cation was sorbed in a weaker manner in comparison to the hydrophobic
534 [C₁₂Chol] cation. Moreover, the addition of PS to the OECD soil contributed to an increase in K_f values
535 from 3.8 to approx. 4.0-4.4 $\text{mg}^{1-1/n}\text{L}^{1/n}/\text{g}$ for [Chol] cation and from 281 to approx. 319-389 $\text{mg}^{1-1/n}\text{L}^{1/n}/\text{g}$
536 for [C₁₂Chol] cation. Nevertheless, for both cations, the following trend is visible: the K_f value increases
537 incrementally from PS < OECD soil < OECD+PS soil systems as presented in Figure 5.

538 Analogously, studies performed by other researchers have also reported an increase in the K_f value in
539 systems enriched with microplastics (Chen et al., 2022; Uber et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020). For
540 example, the $\log K_f$ for triclosan in soil was computed to be 2.20 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}/(\text{mg}/\text{L})^n$), while the addition of
541 PS increased the $\log K_f$ to 2.83 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}/(\text{mg}/\text{L})^n$). Furthermore, the hydrophobic [C₁₂Chol] cation can
542 potentially bind in an even stronger manner to the soil when PS is present. A similar trend was also
543 noted for the hydrophilic [Chol] cation, but there were two orders of magnitude differences between the
544 K_f values for the hydrophilic [Chol] cation and the hydrophobic [C₁₂Chol] cation (Figure 5). In other
545 research, similar K_f values were reported for the investigation of the sorption of ILs based on the
546 glyphosate anion, namely [Chol][Glyph] and [C₁₂Chol][Glyph] (Parus et al., 2023), as well as ILs based
547 on the [Chol] cation and the dicamba herbicide in the soil (Parus et al., 2022).

548

549 **Figure 5.** K_f values determined for [Chol] (a) and [C₁₂Chol] (b) cations for PS and OECD soil, both with
550 and without PS. Please note the different scales used on graphs (a) and (b).

551

552 It deserves to be mentioned that there are many studies that have been devoted to the sorption of
553 xenobiotics on microplastics in aqueous environments (Fang et al., 2019; Guo et al., 2019; Guo and
554 Wang, 2019; Lan et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019).

555 Moreover, one should point out that surface active cations undergo specific interactions due to their
556 amphiphilic structures. Essentially, these surfactants create micelles as well as aggregates that are held
557 together through Van der Waals forces. In such a case, the presence of the anion has a very large
558 influence on the shape of the generated micelle as well as the concentration of the micelles. Thus, this
559 can cause an overriding effect on several interactions with various cells. Furthermore, the changes in the
560 nanostructure (eg. the micelle or its aggregates) are not emphasised enough, since this can potentially

561 lead to invalid observations. Should the nanostructure change, one can claim that the particular structural
562 adjustment is due to the anion's presence. In reality, it can be attributed to the different behaviour of the
563 cation.

564 This is attributed to the fact that the IL is not analysed independently, but instead the ionic solution is
565 assessed. It is important to note, that the unique properties of ILs result from the interaction between the
566 cations and anions due to a disruption in the crystallographic structure. This can be especially seen when
567 ILs are a liquid phase below a temperature 100 °C.

568 Yet, when water is introduced into such a system, many of the present ions undergo solvation. This is
569 particularly evident in solutions consisting of chlorides, bromides and quaternary ammonium cations.
570 Resultingly, a mixture of anions and cations develops in the aqueous solutions.

571 It is indeed difficult to describe the toxicity of ILs if such unique interactions between cations and anions
572 do not truly exist. There is a minimal number of scientific reports that have deeply investigated the study
573 of the toxicity of hydrophobic ILs. Unfortunately, it is difficult to formulate an indestructible cation and
574 anion pair, thus such studies are quite complex.

575 Moreover, hydrophilic ILs yield to dissociation and solvation processes. Only in the case of hydrophobic
576 ILs, is it possible to expect strong interactions between the cations and anions. Yet, such a type of
577 substance would be insoluble in water, hence creating a separate phase. This would therefore behave
578 analogously to the common non-ionic pollutants, such as DDT or dioxins.

579 The issue of the integrity of ionic pairs can be applied further to the natural environment. The majority
580 of ILs studied by researchers involved the introduction of quaternary ammonium cations with inorganic
581 anions into the natural environment. This automatically means that in aqueous systems, we often witness
582 the behaviour of cationic surface-active compounds or solvated cations, which have been described by
583 previous research regarding the fate of cationic surface-active compounds in a natural setting.

584 It is very rare to analyse ILs in which the considered cation and anion were both organic substances and
585 were traced simultaneously.

586 Nevertheless, it should be emphasized that the presence of microplastics in the soil can have a significant
587 impact on the rate of other processes, such as the biodegradation of xenobiotics (Sun et al., 2018).

588 A notable example that can elucidate these mechanisms further, involves the studies of using ¹³C
589 herbicidal ILs (Wilms et al., 2020a). The analysis of the aqueous system as well as the soil, indicated
590 that the cation and anion pair are indeed degraded and mineralised independently of each other. Hence,
591 this suggests that in the environment, the interactions between cations and anions cease to exist. Thus,
592 it is difficult to classify ILs as ionic liquids in the natural environment, since they are a mixture of
593 separately acting cations and anions.

594 Moreover, further tests regarding the sorption were focused on the ability to influence the mobility of
595 an organic anion through pairing it with an appropriate hydrophobic organic cation. The results
596 supported the statement that hydrophobic cations are indeed sorbed in the soil. Simultaneously, the
597 hydrophilic anions do not undergo any particular sorption changes. Likewise, it is necessary to
598 emphasise that the results yielded for the sorption tests show that after ILs dissolve in water, they
599 dissociate into ions which are subsequently solvated (Parus et al., 2023, 2022; Woźniak-Karczewska et
600 al., 2022). There is no tangible proof to believe that such an occurrence is identical in every solvent; for
601 example, in a methanol solvent, one can see a clear quantitative difference between the degree of
602 dissociation and the degree of solvation. Yet, these are undeniably theoretical considerations since using
603 any other solvent but water in the natural environment is completely impractical and unrealistic.

604 Also, NMR analyses seem to confirm that, in many cases, ILs are more molecular mixtures than actual
605 ion pairs (Parus et al., 2023). The best example is the liquefaction of herbicides (Shamshina et al., 2021).
606 Such studies step by step support the lack of interaction between IL cations and anions once they are
607 introduced in the environment.

608 Similarly, our studies with polymers indicate that it is difficult to refer to such substances as ionic liquids,
609 since the cations and anions behave entirely independently of each other.

610 Therefore, there is also a great need for further research on the sorption of xenobiotics in the soil in the
611 presence of microplastics. This must be done in order to gain a better insight on the effects that the
612 addition of microplastics have on the sorption processes.

613 At the moment, it seems that the definition of the aqueous solution of ionic liquids needs to be redefined
614 or at least clarified, as probably most of these ILs are multicomponent pollutants which are typical of

615 mixed systems, such as municipal wastewater, in which we can easily find a lot of organic cations and
616 anions; certainly, we would not classify them as ionic liquids.

617

618 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

619 This undertaken research investigated the effect of the polystyrene microplastic on the sorption of two
620 ionic liquids, namely [Chol][2,4-D] and [C₁₂Chol][2,4-D], in an OECD soil. The results presented here
621 highlight the potential ability of polystyrene microplastics to alter the basic properties of the soil's
622 physicochemical environment, which can promote further functional changes in the soil.

623 The introduction of PS microplastics contributed to an increase in the sorption capacity of the soil
624 complex as well as a 3-5 % increase in the sorption of both cations. Moreover, the sorption analysis
625 revealed that the type of soil has a decisive influence on the sorption efficiency for both [Chol] and
626 [C₁₂Chol] cations.

627 A key finding in our research is that the [2,4-D] anion did not sorb in the soil system even after the
628 addition of microplastics to the soil. This may indicate that the cations and anions, that together form an
629 ionic liquid, are indeed two separately functioning entities in the soil environment.

630 Moreover, the cation sorption had no statistical effect on the [2,4-D] anion's sorption. Therefore, the
631 unique interactions between cations and anions, which are essential in the establishing ILs, are no longer
632 relevant in the sorption on negatively charged soil components. This is compelling evidence, that in the
633 soil environment, the choline-based ionic liquids and the [2,4-D] herbicide do not form an ionic pair.
634 Hence, they undergo physicochemical processes as independent cations and anions. It is worth noting
635 that when planning studies using microplastics, the detailed physicochemical characteristics of such
636 potential sorption material should be taken into account, as it is crucial. We certainly hope that the above
637 study will bring to the foreground the need for further scientific research of ILs, additionally raising the
638 issue of the undeniable stability of ionic liquids in the natural environment.

639

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641

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648

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